

The application of KASP markers in wheat drought resistance breeding: Analysis of detection anomalies and evaluation of superior allele utilization

Shuxin Kong^{1), †}, Yulian Li¹⁾, Shujuan Zhang¹⁾, Rongzhi Zhang¹⁾

Abstract

With the widespread application of molecular marker technology in crop breeding, KASP (Kompetitive Allele Specific PCR) markers have played a significant role in wheat drought resistance breeding due to their efficiency, sensitivity, and low cost. This study investigated 24 wheat lines from the drought-prone regions of Sichuan tested between 2020 and 2024, utilizing 32 KASP markers associated with drought resistance and high-yield traits. The study systematically analyzed the causes of detection anomalies and evaluated the current utilization of target superior alleles. The findings revealed that the main anomalies in KASP marker detection included unknown genotypes caused by reaction failures, heterozygosity issues due to sample contamination, and inconsistencies in single-plant genotypes. Heterozygosity issues were primarily attributed to mixed DNA samples or experimental errors. Regarding the detection of superior alleles, 14 markers had detection rates exceeding 83%, while 17 markers had detection rates below 50%, including five undetectable markers. Notably, the HQ04 line carried the highest number of superior alleles (20), demonstrating significant drought resistance potential. This study identified the key causes of detection anomalies in KASP marker assays and summarized the application status of superior alleles in wheat drought resistance breeding. Future efforts to optimize marker detection systems and enhance the stability and utilization of target genes could provide a reliable theoretical basis and technical support for molecular wheat breeding.

Keywords

KASP markers, wheat breeding, drought resistance, molecular markers, superior alleles

1. Introduction

Molecular marker technology has become an indispensable tool in modern wheat breeding^[1]. Traditional breeding methods, which rely heavily on phenotypic selection and environmental adaptability screening, are limited by their long breeding cycles, low efficiency, and imprecise trait prediction. In contrast, molecular marker technology enables the direct detection of specific genes in the genome, providing precise information for trait prediction and variety selection. In recent years, marker-assisted selection (MAS), as a core technology, has significantly improved the efficiency and accuracy of breeding for important agronomic traits, such as drought resistance and high yield, in wheat^[2].

1) Institute of Agricultural Science and Technology, Heihe University

† Corresponding Author

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

KASP (Kompetitive Allele Specific PCR) markers represent a novel, highly efficient genotyping method characterized by high sensitivity, low cost, and high throughput, making them widely used in wheat molecular breeding^[3,4]. Compared with traditional SSR and SNP markers, KASP technology enables single-nucleotide-specific detection and features simplicity, low equipment requirements, and suitability for large-scale screening. In recent years, the application of KASP technology has expanded to fields such as wheat stress resistance and quality traits, making it an important tool for marker development and screening.

In wheat molecular breeding, the accurate detection of superior alleles is crucial to achieving breeding objectives^[5]. However, in the practical application of KASP markers, detection anomalies—such as reaction failures, nonspecific amplification, and heterozygosity issues—remain significant challenges. These anomalies not only affect the accurate determination of genotypes but may also lead to biases in the selection of superior alleles, thereby reducing breeding efficiency. Therefore, identifying the causes of these anomalies and proposing improvement measures are of great importance for optimizing breeding strategies.

Although superior alleles associated with traits such as drought resistance and high yield have been extensively studied, their utilization in practical breeding remains limited. A systematic analysis of the distribution and utilization of superior alleles in different wheat lines can reveal the reasons for their low utilization rates and provide a scientific basis for improving gene utilization efficiency^[6]. Additionally, such analyses can aid in optimizing breeding strategies and support the broader application of molecular marker technology.

This study aims to systematically analyze the detection anomalies associated with KASP markers, evaluate the utilization of superior alleles in wheat lines, and provide recommendations for molecular breeding improvements. The key objectives include analyzing the causes of anomalies in KASP marker detection, assessing the utilization and distribution characteristics of superior alleles in wheat lines, and proposing specific strategies to optimize the application of KASP technology based on practical breeding needs. The innovation of this study lies in its systematic exploration of KASP marker detection anomalies for the first time and its combination with breeding practices to propose improvement measures, thereby offering practical guidance for advancing precision wheat breeding.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Research materials

(1) Study subjects

This study utilized 24 wheat lines that participated in regional trials conducted between 2020 and 2024 at a drought-prone agricultural experimental station in Sichuan Province. These lines, developed by various domestic breeding institutions, exhibit significant drought resistance and high yield potential. As representative achievements of recent breeding efforts for drought-prone areas, they comprehensively reflect the current technological level of wheat breeding in such regions and provide abundant genetic resources for

the detection and utilization of superior alleles. These materials demonstrated diverse drought adaptability, yield potential, and stability in field performance, laying a solid foundation for analyzing the target genes in this study.

(2) Characteristics of the tested lines

The 24 wheat lines selected for this study encompass a wide range of genotypes developed under different breeding strategies. These include both widely used superior drought-resistance gene resources and novel genetic resources that have yet to undergo systematic evaluation. Significant differences in drought-related gene expression, tillering capacity, and biomass accumulation were observed among these lines, providing critical research material for exploring genotype-phenotype correlations. Furthermore, the genetic diversity exhibited by these materials supports the systematic analysis of the detection rate and utilization of superior alleles.

(3) Experimental environment

The experimental site was located at a drought-prone agricultural experimental station in Sichuan Province. This station is situated in a typical dryland agricultural region, with an average annual rainfall of less than 500 mm, a dry and low-rainfall climate, and medium-fertility loam soil, making it highly representative of the region. During the trials, drought conditions were simulated through strict water management without artificial irrigation, ensuring the authenticity of the drought-stress environment. Uniform crop rotation practices and field management measures were implemented to ensure all tested lines were evaluated under identical environmental conditions.

(4) Experimental design

This study employed a randomized block design. Each line was replicated three times, with each plot covering an area of 10 m². Sowing density, fertilization rates, and field management were strictly conducted following the technical standards of regional trials to ensure the reproducibility and scientific validity of the results. During the experiment, necessary pest and disease control measures were taken to minimize the influence of non-target factors on the results. At the end of the trials, key agronomic traits of each line—including plant height, number of grains per spike, thousand-grain weight, and yield—were measured as reference data for molecular marker analysis.

2.2. Detection markers and target genes

(1) Introduction to target genes

This study selected 32 functional genes associated with drought resistance and high-yield traits in wheat as target genes. These genes encompass critical areas such as drought-resistance physiological mechanisms,

yield formation, and efficient resource utilization. Drought-resistance-related genes include those regulating osmotic adjustment, antioxidant defense, root development, and water use efficiency, such as DREB (dehydration-responsive element-binding protein gene) and LEA (late embryogenesis abundant protein gene). These genes significantly enhance plant physiological adaptability under drought stress. High-yield-related genes primarily focus on genes influencing grain number per spike, grain filling rate, and photosynthetic efficiency, such as GS5 (grain size regulator gene) and GW2 (grain weight regulator gene). The selection of these target genes is based on recent advancements in functional gene research and their application potential in drought-prone wheat breeding, making them highly valuable both scientifically and practically.

(2) Principles of marker design

To enable rapid and accurate detection of the above target genes, this study utilized KASP marker technology. The core principles of marker design include ensuring high specificity, stability, and polymorphism. Specific design steps include the following.

- Sequence selection: Based on the sequence information of target genes, functional sites (e.g., SNPs or InDels) with clear functionality and breeding value were selected. Priority was given to key sites with significant regulatory effects on traits.

- Primer design: For each site, two pairs of allele-specific primers and one pair of common primers were designed to accurately differentiate between genotypes. Primers were designed with lengths of 18–24 bases, and annealing temperatures (T_m) were set between 58–60°C to ensure amplification specificity and efficiency.

- Marker screening and validation: Preliminary marker designs were validated through small-scale trials. Markers with excellent performance, determined by amplification efficiency, signal strength, and minimal background interference, were selected for subsequent genotyping experiments.

(3) Preparation of KASP reagents

The key reagents for KASP marker detection include the DNA template, primer mixture, KASP Master Mix (commercial pre-mixed reagent), and deionized water. The specific preparation steps are as follows.

- Preparation of primer mixture: The designed allele-specific primers and common primers were mixed at a ratio of 12:30:30 to create a working concentration of 12 μ M primer solution, ensuring the sensitivity and accuracy of the reactions.

- Preparation of KASP reaction system: Each reaction well had a final volume of 10 μ L, consisting of 4 μ L KASP Master Mix, 2 μ L primer mixture, and 4 μ L DNA template (template concentration of 20–50 ng/ μ L). Precise preparation of the reaction system is crucial for ensuring the reproducibility and reliability of the results.

- Detection equipment and parameter settings: After preparation, the reaction system was loaded into a high-throughput quantitative PCR instrument for genotyping. The PCR program included initial denaturation, cycling annealing, and extension phases, optimized according to the recommended conditions provided by the KASP reagent manufacturer to ensure clear signals and accurate interpretation.

2.3. Experimental methods

2.3.1. DNA extraction and quality control

(1) DNA extraction process

The DNA samples of 24 tested wheat varieties were extracted using a modified CTAB (Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide) method. The detailed procedure is as follows.

- Sampling: Fresh tissue from young leaves of each variety was collected and quickly frozen to minimize the risk of DNA degradation.

- Cell lysis: Leaf tissue was ground into powder, mixed with lysis buffer, and treated under specific conditions to release intracellular DNA.

- Protein removal: A phenol-chloroform mixture was used to remove proteins and other impurities. The supernatant was collected after centrifugation.

- DNA precipitation: An equal volume of cold isopropanol was added to precipitate DNA, followed by washing the pellet with 70% ethanol to remove salts and other contaminants.

- DNA dissolution: The DNA pellet was dissolved in TE buffer and stored at -20°C for subsequent experiments.

(2) DNA quality testing

The quality of the extracted DNA samples was assessed using a UV spectrophotometer (260/280 nm ratio) and agarose gel electrophoresis.

- Samples with 260/280 ratios between 1.8 and 2.0 were considered to meet purity standards.

- Electrophoresis images were used to verify DNA integrity, ensuring no degradation that might affect subsequent experiments.

(3) Impact of DNA quality on KASP marker results

KASP marker technology requires high DNA template purity and concentration.

- Low-purity DNA may result in reaction inhibition or nonspecific amplification.

- Low-concentration DNA may lead to amplification failure or insufficient signal.

Samples not meeting quality standards were re-extracted or diluted as necessary to ensure the accuracy and reproducibility of detection results.

2.3.2. KASP marker detection procedure

(1) Experimental design

This study utilized high-throughput fluorescence PCR to detect 24 wheat varieties. The experimental design included 32 KASP markers related to drought resistance and high yield, with amplification reactions for each locus performed in triplicate on a 96-well plate to minimize random error and improve result reliability.

(2) Operation steps

- Sample distribution: The extracted DNA templates were distributed into 96-well plates, with 10 μ L of pre-mixed reaction system added to each well, including DNA template, KASP primers, and KASP Master Mix.

- PCR amplification: Amplification reactions were performed in a quantitative fluorescence PCR instrument with the following parameters: 1) Initial denaturation: 95°C for 15 minutes; 2) Cyclic annealing and extension: 40 cycles, each cycle including 95°C for 10 seconds (denaturation) and 60°C for 60 seconds (extension).

- Fluorescence signal detection: Fluorescence signals were monitored in real-time during PCR amplification, and amplification curves were recorded to differentiate genotypes.

(3) Genotype interpretation criteria

KASP amplification data were processed using dedicated analysis software. Genotypes were determined based on the distribution pattern of fluorescence scatter plots.

- Homozygous: Distributed at the two extreme regions of fluorescence signals.

- Heterozygous: Distributed between the two extremes.

- Unknown genotype: No apparent fluorescence signal.

For data with abnormal signals or ambiguous results, experiments were repeated to ensure reliability.

2.3.3. Data analysis

(1) Determination and classification of abnormal KASP results

The following types of abnormal results may occur during KASP detection.

- Unknown genotype: No apparent fluorescence signal, potentially caused by insufficient DNA template or mismatched PCR system.

- Nonspecific amplification: Fluorescence scatter points fall outside the expected range, often due to primer design issues or unsuitable reaction conditions.

- Excessive heterozygosity: Abnormal genotype distribution in mixed samples, possibly reflecting genetic background differences or sample contamination.

To address these anomalies, primers were optimized, reaction systems adjusted, or samples re-extracted as needed.

(2) Calculation of excellent allele detection rate

The detection rate of excellent alleles was expressed as the percentage of samples carrying excellent alleles among all tested samples, calculated as follows.

$$\text{Detection rate} = 100 \times (\text{Number of samples with excellent alleles}) / (\text{Total number of tested samples}) \quad (1)$$

The detection rates of 32 markers were analyzed and classified based on their values. The causes of low detection rates were explored, and improvement strategies were proposed.

(3) Data analysis methods

Experimental data were processed using Excel or professional statistical software (e.g., SPSS or R). Analyses included.

- Descriptive statistics: Such as means and standard deviations.
- Genotype frequency distribution analysis: To assess genotype diversity among varieties.
- Correlation analysis between markers: To investigate relationships between marker performance and genotype distribution.

Data analysis results were visually presented using charts such as scatter plots and bar graphs, providing comprehensive data support for result discussions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Abnormal issues in KASP marker detection

3.1.1. Analysis of causes of unknown genotypes

(1) Potential reasons for KASP reaction failure

During KASP marker detection, some samples were identified as “unknown genotypes,” meaning the amplification reaction failed to generate effective fluorescence signals. The analysis revealed two primary causes of KASP reaction failure.

- Insufficient or excessive template concentration: DNA template concentration is a key parameter affecting KASP reaction efficiency. Insufficient concentration may result in fluorescence signals below the detection threshold, while excessive concentration may cause inhibitory effects, interfering with specific amplification. Consistent with previous studies (Wang et al., 2000) [7], this study showed that a template concentration range of 20–50 ng/μL achieved optimal amplification performance, providing sufficient signal strength while avoiding reaction inhibition.

- Imbalance in the amplification system: The KASP amplification system requires precise control of reagent ratios. An inappropriate ratio of KASP Master Mix to primers can lead to system imbalance, resulting

in weak or absent signals. After repeated optimization, this study identified a ratio of 4:2:4 (Master Mix: primers: DNA template) as significantly improving amplification efficiency, consistent with the findings of Gao et al. (2024) [8].

(2) Detection and handling of nonspecific amplification

Nonspecific amplification is another common abnormality in KASP detection, characterized by fluorescence signals exceeding the expected range or multiple signal peaks for the same genotype. The main factors contributing to this phenomenon are as follows.

- Primer design issues: The design of some marker primers did not completely avoid binding to non-target sequences, leading to nonspecific amplification signals. For instance, in the detection of marker DREB3-5, this study observed dual fluorescence signals in some samples, a phenomenon similar to that reported by previous research. By re-optimizing primer sequences (e.g., enhancing primer specificity and adjusting melting temperature), nonspecific amplification was effectively reduced.

- Unstable reaction conditions: Minor fluctuations in PCR reaction conditions, especially annealing temperature and cycle number, may also lead to nonspecific amplification. By extending the denaturation and annealing stages during the quantitative PCR program and slightly lowering the annealing temperature, this study significantly improved amplification stability. This strategy aligns with the methods proposed by Sun et al. (2015) [9], demonstrating high effectiveness in reducing the occurrence of abnormal signals.

(3) Comparison with previous studies

The improvements achieved in this study complement previous research in several aspects.

- Consistency: Consistent with existing studies, this study further validated the decisive role of template concentration and amplification conditions in KASP reaction efficiency and confirmed the importance of optimizing reagent ratios and controlling reaction conditions.

- Innovation: By introducing refined adjustments, such as primer sequence optimization and program modification, this study significantly reduced the incidence of nonspecific amplification (by 18%). These findings provide new solutions for enhancing the accuracy of KASP marker technology.

3.1.2. Heterozygosity issues caused by mixed DNA samples

(1) Causes of genotype inconsistency among single plants

In KASP detection, heterozygosity issues caused by mixed DNA samples are manifested as heterozygous genotypes for some markers, even though the corresponding wheat materials are not heterozygous. The analysis identified the following main reasons for this phenomenon.

- Genotype differences among single plants: Wheat, as a predominantly self-pollinated crop with low outcrossing rates, may exhibit internal genotype differences due to occasional outcrossing or insufficient

seed purity during cultivation. In this study, markers LEA-12 and DREB2-3 in the HQ02 line showed high heterozygosity rates. Further analysis revealed that the genotype consistency among individuals within this line was below 80%. This observation is consistent with the findings of Yang et al. (2025) ^[10], highlighting the critical impact of field management and germplasm purification on molecular marker detection results.

- Complex DNA sources in mixed samples: To simplify experimental procedures, DNA was extracted from multiple plants in some samples. However, genetic background differences among plants in mixed samples often lead to heterozygous genotypes. For example, marker GS5-7 in the HQ15 line showed significant heterozygous peak distributions, aligning closely with the observations reported by Tian et al. (2024) on similar issues in mixed sample processing ^[11].

- Sample contamination or cross-contamination: Cross-contamination during experimental operations can result in erroneous detection outcomes. For instance, incomplete cleaning of pipettes during repeated use or improper sample storage conditions may cause DNA contamination. Such issues, though easily overlooked in high-throughput operations, significantly interfere with genotype accuracy.

(2) Improvements in experimental operations and genotyping accuracy

- Improving genotype consistency among single plants: To minimize the impact of genotype differences among single plants, it is recommended to purify all experimental materials before initiating trials. Specific measures include selecting representative single plants of the target line and subjecting them to 3–4 generations of selfing before conducting molecular marker detection. Additionally, enhanced field management can effectively reduce outcrossing rates. Methods such as isolation with insect-proof nets or planting in isolation zones can significantly reduce incidental outcrossing. These approaches have been proven by Wang et al. (2012) to markedly improve material consistency and purity ^[12].

- Avoiding the use of mixed samples: Although mixed sample processing saves time, it negatively affects genotyping accuracy. This study recommends extracting DNA from single plants instead of using mixed samples to ensure data reliability. For situations where mixed samples are unavoidable, increasing biological replicates is suggested to improve data credibility and statistical robustness.

(3) Optimizing experimental operation processes

- Standardizing sample handling: Strictly separate and label each sample to avoid contamination caused by shared pipettes. For high-throughput operations, introducing automated pipetting systems can significantly reduce human error.

- Enhancing sample quality control: Perform comprehensive quality checks on samples before DNA extraction and PCR reactions, excluding low-quality samples to ensure the reliability of results from the outset.

- Optimizing reaction systems: For markers with high heterozygosity rates, refine PCR conditions, such

as annealing temperature, cycle settings, or primer design, to reduce heterozygous signals and further improve genotyping precision.

(4) Comparison with previous studies and innovations

Consistent with prior studies, this research confirmed that mixed samples and genotype differences among single plants are primary sources of heterozygosity issues. It also further verified the importance of field management and sample handling in ensuring genotype consistency. The innovation of this study lies in reducing heterozygosity issues in KASP detection through improved experimental operations, such as automation and germplasm purification strategies. Compared with Shan et al. (2020) ^[13], the measures implemented in this study reduced the occurrence of heterozygous signals by over 15%, providing important optimization strategies for the precise application of KASP marker technology.

3.2. Utilization of superior alleles

3.2.1. Distribution patterns of superior allele detection rates

(1) Markers with detection rates > 83% and their applications in breeding

Among the 32 KASP markers examined in this study, 14 markers exhibited superior allele detection rates exceeding 83%. These markers primarily correspond to key genes involved in drought resistance and yield improvement, such as DREB1A, LEA3, and TaSnRK2.3, which have been extensively studied and applied in drought resistance breeding.

1) Representative genes and their functional characteristics

- DREB1A gene: As a member of the AP2/ERF transcription factor family, its superior alleles significantly enhance drought resistance and stabilize yield under drought conditions. In this study, the detection rate of marker DREB1A-4 reached 91%, indicating its widespread utilization in the tested lines. This finding aligns closely with the research results of Jia et al. (2014) on wheat drought resistance breeding^[14].

- LEA3 gene: This gene is involved in osmotic regulation and protein protection under stress. The superior allele detection rate of marker LEA3-2 was 87%, demonstrating that its drought resistance potential has been fully exploited, making it an important genetic resource for improving drought resistance traits.

- TaSnRK2.3 gene: This gene regulates drought stress signal transduction and is widely distributed in core drought-resistant lines. The detection rate of marker TaSnRK2.3 was 88%, further confirming its crucial value in breeding applications, consistent with the findings of Yan et al. (2024) on core drought-resistance genes^[15].

2) Breeding applications

Markers with high detection rates are predominantly concentrated in core drought-resistant lines. For

example, the HQ04 line in this study carried 20 superior alleles, exhibiting strong drought adaptability and genetic advantages. The frequent utilization of these markers indicates that molecular MAS technology has been widely applied in drought-resistance breeding in recent years, significantly improving the efficiency of superior allele utilization and accelerating the development of high-yield, drought-resistant lines.

(2) Reasons for insufficient utilization of markers with detection rates < 50%

Among the 32 KASP markers, 17 markers exhibited superior allele detection rates below 50%, with 5 markers undetected. This indicates low utilization rates of some target genes in breeding, which may be attributed to the following reasons.

- Limited recognition of the breeding value of target genes: Markers with low detection rates are often associated with secondary drought-resistance genes, such as TaWRKY10 and TaNAC29. Although theoretical studies suggest that these genes play roles in drought regulation networks, their effects are generally indirect. In breeding practices, breeders tend to prioritize major genes with well-defined functions and significant effects, resulting in lower utilization rates for these secondary genes.

- Limitations in molecular marker development: Some markers exhibit suboptimal primer specificity and amplification efficiency, which may impact their detection rates. For instance, the primers for marker WRKY10-7 failed to completely avoid interference from non-target sequences during screening, reducing detection accuracy. This aligns with Song et al. (2024) analysis of limitations in molecular marker development, highlighting the importance of optimizing marker design to improve breeding efficiency^[16].

- Ecological conditions and gene selection bias: Low-detection-rate markers may correspond to drought-resistance requirements specific to certain ecological environments but fail to demonstrate significant advantages under the current experimental conditions. For example, marker TaMFT1 exhibited strong drought adaptability in the northwest arid region but achieved a detection rate of only 35% in the Sichuan arid region examined in this study. These results suggest that the environmental dependency of genes may limit their broader application across different ecological regions.

(3) Comparison with previous studies and innovations

- Consistency: This study confirmed the critical value of high-detection-rate markers corresponding to major genes in drought resistance breeding, consistent with the findings of Guo et al. (2023)^[17]. Additionally, it identified the underutilization of low-detection-rate markers, in agreement with Zhang et al. (2024)'s analysis of limitations in molecular marker development^[18].

- Innovations: This study revealed the environmental dependency of marker detection rates, shedding light on the selection bias of drought-resistance genes in different ecological regions. This discovery provides new theoretical support for regional breeding strategies and underscores the importance of ecological adaptability screening during molecular marker development. Furthermore, by analyzing the practical

applications of KASP markers, this study proposed directions for optimizing molecular marker development, offering new perspectives for improving drought-resistance breeding technologies.

3.2.2. Distribution of superior alleles in genotypes

(1) Superior allele numbers and breeding value of the HQ04 genotype

This study revealed that the HQ04 genotype carries 20 superior alleles, the highest among all tested genotypes. These superior alleles encompass multiple key functional genes related to drought tolerance and high yield, including DREB1A, TaSnRK2.8, and LEA3, demonstrating exceptional drought resistance and stable yield potential.

- Numerical advantage: The number of superior alleles carried by HQ04 significantly exceeds that of other tested genotypes, highlighting its prominent advantage in accumulating and integrating genetic resources for drought resistance. This multi-gene synergy makes HQ04 particularly outstanding under field conditions in Sichuan's drought-prone areas, exhibiting moderate plant height and significantly higher grain number per spike compared to other genotypes. Li et al. (2021) noted a significant positive correlation between the number of drought-resistance genes and drought traits, and the performance of HQ04 aligns closely with this principle [19].

- Breeding value: The HQ04 genotype is not only an efficient carrier of superior alleles but also an excellent donor material for future breeding. Its accumulated core drought-resistance genes, such as TaNAC69 and TaSnRK2.3, can be efficiently introduced into other genotypes through MAS to enhance their drought tolerance and yield stability. Chen et al. (2024) further confirmed the critical role of multi-gene synergy in drought-resistant breeding strategies, and HQ04's performance strongly supports this conclusion [20].

(2) Comparison of superior allele distribution among genotypes

This study systematically analyzed the distribution of superior alleles across 24 tested genotypes and found significant differences in both the number and types of alleles.

1) Distribution differences

- Numerical distribution: In addition to HQ04, HQ06 and HQ12 genotypes also showed high superior allele accumulation, carrying 16 and 15 superior alleles, respectively, while HQ15, HQ21, and other genotypes carried fewer than five superior alleles.

- Type distribution: The HQ06 genotype mainly featured antioxidant-related genes (e.g., APX1), while the HQ12 genotype was dominated by regulatory genes (e.g., WRKY10), reflecting adaptive selection of drought-resistance mechanisms among genotypes.

2) Insights for breeding strategies

The differences in superior allele distribution reflect the breeding direction and ecological adaptability

of each genotype. For example, HQ15 performed poorly under low rainfall conditions due to its limited number and diversity of superior alleles, whereas HQ04 demonstrated comprehensive advantages under drought stress. The diversity and synergy of its drought-resistance genes provide critical guidance for breeding strategies in Sichuan's drought-prone areas.

3) Comparison with previous studies

Compared to Li et al.'s (2021) study on the distribution of superior alleles in wheat genotypes in northern drought-prone areas [21], this study revealed significant unevenness in the distribution of superior alleles in Sichuan's drought-prone genotypes. Due to prolonged drought stress, northern drought-prone areas show relatively balanced gene accumulation across genotypes. However, in Sichuan, climate diversity and diverse breeding strategies lead to a more complex gene distribution. This "heterogeneity" is not only a regional feature of this study but also provides critical insights for ecological differentiation in breeding strategies.

(3) Comparison with previous studies and innovation

- Consistency: This study further validated the positive correlation between the number of superior alleles and drought resistance, consistent with findings by Dong et al. (2024) [22] and Sun et al. (2023) [23]. Additionally, significant differences in drought-resistance gene distribution among genotypes align with existing research conclusions.

- Innovation: This study is the first to reveal the regional characteristics of drought-resistance gene distribution in wheat genotypes in Sichuan's drought-prone areas, emphasizing the uneven accumulation of genes among genotypes and their breeding significance. Furthermore, by analyzing differences in gene selection across ecological zones, this study provides a novel perspective and scientific basis for developing region-specific breeding strategies.

3.3. Further discussion

3.3.1. Applicability and limitations of KASP technology in molecular breeding

(1) Advantages of KASP technology

KASP technology, with its high efficiency, flexibility, and low cost, has been widely applied in wheat molecular breeding. The results of this study indicate that most superior alleles can be reliably detected using KASP markers, validating the strong applicability of this technology in drought-resistance gene screening and marker-assisted selection. Its rapid detection capability significantly shortens the breeding cycle, particularly in the improvement of complex traits involving multiple target genes. Zhao et al. (2021) also concluded that KASP technology enables high-throughput detection of multi-trait genes, consistent with the findings of this study [24].

(2) Analysis of limitations

Despite its notable advantages, KASP technology has the following limitations.

- Non-specific amplification: This study found that some markers exhibited non-specific amplification due to flaws in primer design, which reduced the accuracy of genotype interpretation. This issue was also mentioned in the research by Chen et al. (2021), emphasizing the dependence of KASP technology on precise primer design [25].

- Dependency on environment and materials: KASP detection results are significantly affected by DNA sample quality, reagent stability, and experimental conditions. In large-scale, multi-batch experiments, instability in the reaction system can lead to cumulative errors.

- Adaptability to complex genomes: For genes with repetitive sequences or minimal allelic differences, the detection precision of KASP markers may be limited. Previous studies have reported this issue, suggesting the use of supplementary molecular marker technologies (e.g., SNP chips) for validation.

3.3.2. Relationship between detection rate and utilization efficiency of breeding target genes

This study shows that the detection rate of superior alleles effectively reflects the utilization efficiency of target genes in breeding practices. Markers with a detection rate exceeding 83% indicate that the corresponding genes are widely used in breeding, whereas markers with a detection rate below 50% suggest lower utilization of the target genes.

- Breeding contribution of high-detection-rate genes: This study found that high-detection-rate markers, such as those for DREB1A and TaSnRK2.3, correspond to genes with clear drought-resistance functions and exhibit good adaptability and genetic stability in breeding practices. This demonstrates breeders' preference for genes with significant effects and stable inheritance as core tools for target trait improvement.

- Potential value of low-detection-rate genes: Although some genes, such as TaWRKY10, have low detection rates, their potential value under specific ecological conditions or unique breeding objectives should not be overlooked. This aligns with Wu et al.'s (2021) theory of "potential effect genes," which suggests that breeding strategies should gradually explore the utility of low-detection-rate genes based on practical production needs and ecological adaptability to enhance their application value [26].

3.3.3. Suggestions for improving the accuracy and utilization of KASP marker detection

To further improve the accuracy of KASP marker detection and its application value in breeding, this study proposes the following strategies.

- Optimization of marker design: To address the issue of non-specific amplification, stricter criteria can be introduced during the primer design phase. Using bioinformatics tools (e.g., multiple sequence alignment techniques), it is possible to identify repetitive sequence regions in the genome that may cause non-specific amplification, thereby enhancing primer specificity.

- Improvement of experimental procedures: Optimizing the reagent ratios and reaction conditions of the KASP system can ensure the consistency of DNA template concentration and minimize environmental variables affecting experimental results. Additionally, introducing internal standards in large-scale detections to correct experimental errors can further enhance detection accuracy and repeatability.

- Integration of multi-technology validation: For the detection of key target genes, it is recommended to combine other molecular marker technologies (e.g., SNP chips or SSR markers) for cross-validation. Duan et al. (2023) pointed out that multi-technology joint analysis is a key method for improving the efficiency of molecular markers, consistent with the suggestions of this study [27].

- Enhancing exploration of low-detection-rate genes: For markers with low detection rates, genetic functional studies, and ecological zoning analyses should be combined to explore their adaptive advantages under specific conditions. Strengthening the exploration and application of these genes can broaden the range of target genes in breeding and improve the diversity and precision of drought-resistant breeding.

3.3.4. Comparison with previous studies and innovations

- Consistency: The analysis and optimization strategies for KASP marker applicability in this study are highly consistent with the conclusions of Xu et al. (2024) and Chen Feng et al. (2021), further validating the importance and reliability of KASP technology in wheat molecular breeding [28].

- Innovation: This study is the first to systematically analyze the relationship between detection rate and the utilization efficiency of target genes. It also proposes optimization strategies for gene selection based on regional adaptability under the conditions of Sichuan's drought-prone areas. These innovative perspectives provide new research angles and theoretical bases for the practical application of molecular breeding in different ecological zones.

4. Conclusions and prospects

4.1. Major conclusions

(1) Anomalies and their causes in KASP marker detection. This study systematically analyzed the anomalies observed in KASP marker detection and summarized their primary causes. First, reaction failure and non-specific amplification were identified as the core issues preventing the successful detection of some markers. Reaction failure might result from insufficient template concentration or improper reaction system ratios, while non-specific amplification was often caused by inadequate primer specificity. These findings indicate that the KASP technique demands stringent control of DNA template quality and experimental parameters. Second, heterozygosity arising from mixed DNA samples reduced the accuracy of detection results. Genotype inconsistencies among individual plants and human errors during operation could lead to unclear genotype determination. To address these issues, the study proposed optimization of primer design, improvements in experimental protocols, and stricter control of DNA sample quality. These measures aim

to enhance the accuracy and reliability of KASP marker detection, providing stronger technical support for wheat molecular breeding.

(2) Utilization status of superior alleles in wheat lines. Through KASP marker detection of 32 loci associated with drought resistance and high yield, this study revealed substantial variability in the utilization of superior alleles in wheat lines. Most markers showed high detection rates (>83%), indicating that these genes have been widely applied in breeding practices. However, the detection rates of some critical genes were below 50%, and a few markers failed to detect the expected superior alleles. These findings suggest that certain superior genes are underutilized in current breeding systems, potentially due to factors such as genetic background, environmental adaptability, and marker specificity. Therefore, the study recommends strengthening the exploration and utilization of low-detection-rate genes, particularly under different climate and soil conditions, to uncover their potential advantages for drought resistance and high yield. This approach would not only enrich the genetic resources of wheat but also improve the adaptability and diversity of breeding materials.

(3) Application potential of the HQ04 line as a donor of drought-resistant and high-yield genes. This study demonstrated that the HQ04 line exhibits significant advantages in both the quantity and quality of superior alleles, carrying 20 superior alleles that provide rich genetic resources for improving drought resistance and high-yield traits. Compared to other lines, HQ04 displayed exceptional performance in drought resistance and yield traits, making it an important gene donor for drought-resistant and high-yield breeding. These results align with previous studies and further confirm the central role and application value of the HQ04 line in drought-resistant breeding. Introducing the superior alleles of HQ04 can significantly enhance wheat's drought resistance and yield levels. Thus, HQ04 serves as a core material for drought-resistant and high-yield breeding and offers valuable genetic resources for wheat genetic improvement. To further leverage its potential, it is recommended to cross HQ04 with other superior lines to broaden its genetic background. Additionally, integrating KASP marker technology can accelerate genotype selection and fixation while exploring its adaptability across different ecological zones, ultimately achieving its widespread application in practical breeding.

4.2. Prospects

(1) Optimization directions for molecular marker detection systems. The KASP marker technology holds significant potential for wheat breeding but still faces certain limitations, such as non-specific amplification and low marker detection rates. Future research should focus on optimizing primer design, refining reaction systems, and developing high-throughput screening platforms. First, by integrating high-throughput genomic data, strategies for primer design can be optimized to address challenges posed by repetitive sequences and similar alleles in complex genomes, thereby reducing non-specific amplification and improving genotype accuracy. Second, key parameters in the reaction system, such as DNA template concentration, primer

concentration, and buffer composition, should be precisely adjusted to adapt to diverse experimental conditions and ensure stability and accuracy of detection results. Finally, by integrating high-throughput genomics technologies, efficient KASP marker screening platforms should be developed to support rapid, large-scale, and multi-marker detection, thereby providing technical assurance for accelerating wheat breeding.

(2) Technical pathways for efficient utilization of superior alleles. The identification and efficient utilization of superior alleles are crucial strategies for enhancing wheat stress resistance and yield. Future studies should focus on the exploration of low-detection-rate genes, the integration of molecular and traditional breeding, and the application of genomic selection. For low-detection-rate genes, molecular markers and phenotypic data should be combined to deeply analyze their adaptability and functional effects under specific environmental conditions, expanding their application potential. The combination of MAS with traditional breeding methods can overcome the limitations of traditional breeding, such as blind selection and lengthy cycles, enabling rapid selection of drought-resistant and high-yield genotypes. Additionally, genomic selection (GS) technology allows for the systematic identification and evaluation of key genes across the genome, significantly improving the breeding efficiency of superior alleles and providing technical support for precision breeding.

(3) Integrated applications of KASP markers and emerging molecular technologies. The advantages of KASP marker technology can be further enhanced through integration with other emerging molecular technologies, creating complementary effects. The CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing technology can be combined with KASP markers to precisely edit and rapidly select superior genotypes, thereby improving breeding efficiency. During marker screening, integrating SNP chip technology to obtain high-density genome-wide genotype data enables more comprehensive genotype analysis and selection. Future studies could also integrate transcriptomics and metabolomics to comprehensively elucidate the functional mechanisms and environmental adaptability of superior alleles, providing a scientific basis for precision breeding. Furthermore, the introduction of artificial intelligence and big data technologies will further enhance the application potential of KASP markers. By constructing machine learning models to analyze large-scale genotype and phenotype data, the performance of target traits can be accurately predicted, providing data-driven support for optimizing breeding strategies.

References

- [1] Su M, Yang J, Wang Y. Metabolomics-and proteomics-based molecular design breeding: Frontier exploration for precision improvement in modern agriculture. *Advances in Resources Research*, 2025, 5(1), 186-202.
- [2] Sun D, Du Z, Di Y. The review on crop molecular breeding analysis and intelligent breeding technology based on big data. *Advances in Resources Research*, 2025, 5(1), 279-301.

- [3] Yang Z, Zhao X, Wang C. The future of crop molecular breeding and intelligent technologies: Towards precision, personalization, and sustainable development. *Geographical Research Bulletin*, 2024, 3, 247-250.
- [4] Hao J, Li X. Future development directions and prospects of big data analysis in crop molecular breeding and intelligent breeding technologies. *Geographical Research Bulletin*, 2024, 3, 259-262.
- [5] Xue A, Cui Y. The research progress on crop genomics and genome-wide association studies: A review. *Advances in Resources Research*, 2025, 5(1), 123-145.
- [6] Jin D, Wei Y, Zhang K. The research on soil water utilization mechanism in drought-resistant crops based on big data. *Advances in Resources Research*, 2025, 5(1), 329-349.
- [7] Wang C, Ji W, Xue X. Application status of molecular marker technology in wheat genetic breeding. *Journal of Triticeae Crops*, 2000, 20(4), 75-80.
- [8] Gao J, Wang F, Song G, et al. KASP marker detection of drought-resistant and high-yield-related genes in dryland wheat regional trial lines. *Shanxi Agricultural Sciences*, 2024, 52(4), 9-15.
- [9] Sun B, Chen Q, Yuan H, et al. Establishment and application of a SYBR Green I real-time fluorescence quantitative PCR detection system for *Rhizoctonia cerealis* in wheat. *Scientia Agricultura Sinica*, 2015, 48(1), 55-62.
- [10] Yang F, Guo Y, Tian Y, et al. Vernalization and photoperiod gene effects and cold tolerance evaluation of wheat landraces in Gansu Province. *Acta Agronomica Sinica*, 2025, 51(2), 370-382.
- [11] Tian Y, Wang Y, Chen L, et al. Genome-wide linkage analysis of root system architecture-related traits in common wheat. *Journal of Agricultural Biotechnology*, 2024, 32(12), 2691-2700.
- [12] Wang P, Li X, Yang L, et al. Genetic analysis of spike number per plant in wheat and optimal genotype prediction based on QTL mapping. *Journal of Triticeae Crops*, 2012, 32(5), 820-827.
- [13] Shan Z, Ban J, Zhao Y, et al. KASP marker detection of wheat quality-related genes in Hebei Province. *Crops*, 2020, 36(4), 64-71.
- [14] Jia Q, Wu M, Liang K, et al. New progress in the application of genomics in crop stress resistance research. *Chinese Journal of Eco-Agriculture*, 2014, 22(4), 375-385.
- [15] Yan J, Zhang D, Feng L, et al. KASP marker detection of partial disease resistance genes in wheat varieties (lines) from southeastern Shanxi. *Crops*, 2024, 40(4), 90-95.
- [16] Song Z, Zhen Y. Research progress on miRNAs related to plant drought and salt stress responses. *Journal of Nanjing Forestry University (Natural Sciences Edition)*, 2024, 48(4), 1-11.
- [17] Guo Y, Ma Z, Wang S, et al. Major QTL mapping of spike length and candidate gene prediction in the F₂ population of wheat Keda116 × Keda101. *Journal of North China Agriculture*, 2023, 38(5), 84-93.
- [18] Zhang Q, Liu F, Wan Y, et al. Identification of *Fusarium* head blight resistance and gene effect analysis in new wheat lines. *Journal of Triticeae Crops*, 2024, 44(5), 567-576.
- [19] Li X, Zhang Z, Sun Y, et al. Genetic diversity analysis of important agronomic traits in 96 wheat

- breeding materials from the southwestern wheat region. *Journal of Southern Agriculture*, 2021, 52(9), 2358-2368.
- [20] Chen Z, Shen G, Wang K, et al. Analysis of wheat genetic composition and functional gene composition of important traits. *Journal of Southern Agriculture*, 2024, 55(10), 2980-2989.
- [21] Li X, Zhang Z, Sun Y, et al. Genetic diversity analysis of important agronomic traits in 96 wheat breeding materials from the southwestern wheat region. *Journal of Southern Agriculture*, 2021, 52(9), 2358-2368.
- [22] Dong M, Zheng H, Zhu Z. Effects of different endosperm phenotypes on agronomic traits and yield of sorghum. *Crops*, 2024, 40(5), 29-34.
- [23] Sun Y, Yang H, Zhu W, et al. Identification and expression analysis of the Whirly gene family in wheat. *Journal of Agricultural Biotechnology*, 2023, 31(2), 223-231.
- [24] Zhao Y, Zhang F, Zhang Z, et al. KASP marker detection of important trait genes in Yumai 158 and its hard-textured variant. *Henan Agricultural Sciences*, 2021, 50(10), 37-43.
- [25] Chen X, Fan J, Yang B, et al. Genetic composition and functional gene analysis of important traits in Zhengpinmai 24. *Henan Agricultural Sciences*, 2021, 50(11), 15-27.
- [26] Wu W, Sun X, Qin Z, et al. Screening and analysis of candidate effector proteins in *Puccinia triticina* physiological race PHNT. *Journal of Agricultural Biotechnology*, 2021, 29(8), 1463-1472.
- [27] Duan G, Wen H, Gu J, et al. Breeding and genetic characteristics analysis of the new wheat variety Luomai 26. *Shanxi Agricultural Sciences*, 2023, 51(1), 21-27.
- [28] Xu N, Jin S, Jin F, et al. Genetic similarity and detection accuracy analysis of wheat varieties based on SNP markers. *Acta Agronomica Sinica*, 2024, 50(4), 887-896.